

organic molecules. Nevertheless, standardized tests such as OECD 301 and 302 are currently used to assess biodegradability of polymers. However, the degradation mechanism of polymers, which necessitates break down into smaller fragments before microbial uptake and biodegradation, differs significantly from that of small molecules. As a result, existing methodologies and pass criteria may not be appropriate for assessing polymer biodegradation.

The commercially most successful synthetic poly(amino acid) is the water-soluble and anionic poly(aspartic acid). However, little is known about the biodegradability of tPAA. In this study, we investigated the interaction between the hydrolases from *Sphingomonas* sp. KT-1 and *Pedobacter* sp. KP-2, named Ss_hydrolase-1, Ss_hydrolase-2 and Ps_hydrolase-1, with tPAA and effects these enzymes have on tPAA biodegradation. Detailed investigations were performed to understand activities and elucidate synergistic action by using recombinant enzymes on tPAA. Finally, the individual and synergistic effect of the hydrolases have been investigated within an OECD 301 F biodegradation test to showcase the potential of incorporating enzymes within existing standardized test to shorten testing times and better elucidate polymer biodegradation processes. These investigations aim to better understand the role of polymer molecular weight on microbial degradation and how this process is influenced by competent (extracellular) enzymes.

4.02.P-We335 Innovating on polymer degradation: Making two ends meet

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Polymers play a pivotal role in modern society by providing a multitude of technical functionalities in materials and products. They represent a vast and diverse aspect of the chemical space, often characterized by medium to very high molecular sizes and various functionalities. For polymers emitted down the drain, ultimate degradability becomes a favourable property. Yet, assessing the environmental fate of polymers poses scientific challenges, primarily due to their high molecular weight, which leads to low bioavailability impacting for example uptake in biodegradation studies.

In line with their emission routes, polymers used in Home and Personal Care products are evaluated for their biodegradation potential. However, the domain of applicability of standardized test guidelines, such as those from the OECD, does not include polymers. Therefore, the innovation of new materials faces two main challenges. The first is the need to accelerate the development of screening methods to inform product development, while the second is aligned to the need for the adaptation of standardized test methods to widen the applicability domain to polymers. In this presentation, we delve into methodologies for evaluating the biodegradation of polymers in aqueous systems during product development by use of screening and modified test methods.

At early stages of development, combining enzymatic assays with analytical techniques like ¹H NMR spectroscopy enables the characterization of changes in structural features. Additionally, candidate polymers are evaluated using standard or modified OECD biodegradation screenings studies. Adaptions including the extension of the test durations, are valuable approaches in comparing the biodegradation polymers with similar structural properties.

4.02.P-We336 Are Bio-Based Monomers Environmentally Safer Alternatives to Bisphenol A Diglycidyl Ether?

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In the last decades, bio-based epoxy resins have been gained relevance as more environmentally friendly alternatives to traditional petroleum-based epoxy resins, as the latter have proved to constitute serious hazards to the environment. A key challenge on the shift from petroleum-based to bio-based polymers is the replacement of one of the most widely used building monomers for epoxy resins, i.e., the diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA), without affecting the final functionality of the resin. Among the bio-based alternatives to DGEBA, that have been developed and used, is the bisphenol-free diglycidyl ether of vanillyl alcohol (DGEVA SP s catalogue reference SP-9S-5-005 CAS 1584677-14-4) that could be obtained from lignin. In this context, the present work aimed at a comparative characterization of the toxicity of DGEBA and the bio-based monomer DGEVA to freshwater biota. Additionally, the toxicity of cystamine (SP s catalogue reference SP-2-4-001 - CAS 51-85-4), a bio-based hardener (derived from amino acids) also incorporated in epoxy resins, was also assessed. To achieve the established objectives,

the ecotoxicity of DGEBA and the two bio-based monomers was characterized by performing the following assays: 72-h growth rate inhibition with *Raphidocelis subcapitata*, 7-d growth rate inhibition with *Lemna minor*, 24-h acute toxicity assay with *Brachionus calyciflous*, 48-h acute toxicity assay with *Daphnia magna*, and 96-h embryo acute toxicity assay with *Danio rerio*. Overall, DGEVA revealed a lower toxicity, comparatively to DGEBA, for the tested species, with EC50s always above 73 mg/L. Regarding cystamine, no mortality or malformations were observed in *D. rerio*. For the other tested species, the estimated EC50s of cystamine ranged from 6.18 to 63.84 mg/L. In conclusion, the obtained results confirm that DGEVA is a more environmentally safer alternative to DGEBA, thus, supporting the premise that it is a more sustainable bio-based building monomer of epoxy resins.

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4.03.P Statistics for Risk Assessment from Tried and Tested to New and Exciting Methods

4.03.P-Tu316 Applying Generalized Linear Mixed Models (GLMM) for the Evaluation of Ecotoxicological Endpoints in a Regulatory Context: A Framework Demonstrated by a Small Mammal Case Study

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Analysing data from ecotoxicological studies on small mammals to detect and evaluate effects of pesticide applications can be daunting due to the inherent variability of natural systems, the complex interactions between environmental factors, complexities such as non-linear dynamics, and the difficulties working with free ranging wild animals. Regression-based statistical approaches, including generalized linear and additive mixed effect models (GLMM, GAMM), have a long tradition in ecology to disentangle the influence of multiple factors on observed data. Such techniques have also gained attention in analysing data from higher tier enclosure and field studies conducted for environmental pesticide risk assessment. Nevertheless, GLMM analysis are often perceived as complex, leading to hesitation to account for their results in regulatory evaluations.

To enhance the uptake and understanding of GLMM and GAMM by regulators and ecotoxicologists, we aimed to present a structured framework of decision-steps to demystify the preparation, construction, validation, and evaluation of GLMM and GAMMs within the context of ecotoxicological field study data. This framework follows a two-stage approach where significance of treatment-related effects can be checked in both stages. A thorough data exploration, and model interpretation and visualization, complete the framework in a total of 7 steps.

The framework is demonstrated in a case study on voles exposed to a fungicide under field conditions. After exploratory data analysis, model alternatives were developed that are tailored to the different data types (counts, proportions, continuous data) recorded as endpoints of (semi-)field studies, and considering the repeated sampling within the same fields or enclosures and the potential non-linear dynamics of the endpoints over time. Different model alternatives were then compared through model selection, and the statistical power of the model evaluated through post-hoc Minimal Detectable Difference (MDD) testing. A final visualization for each endpoint assisted the interpretation of the statistical results.

The case study demonstrated the usefulness of the framework, to maximize the advantages of GLMM/GAMM analyses, namely, their adaptability to different data types, ability to incorporate all data within a single analysis (while excluding pseudoreplication), and ability to account for multiple influencing factors of direct and indirect interest to the study interpretation.

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4.03.P-Tu317 Four-Parameter Nonlinear Regression and Maximum Achievable Effect in Ecotoxicology: Just Visually Appealing or Biologically Relevant?

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In ecotoxicology, "EC_x" refers to the "concentration that causes x% effect" (OECD 2006). This seems to be a precise definition, but is typically only clear for EC_x values calculated for inhibitions of metric